

INVESTIGATION OF THE ROLE OF SEXUAL CONTENT IN TELEVISION BROADCAST ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN WITHIN THE CONTEXT OF RELATIONS¹

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Abstract

In the current century, there is a close relationship between child development and mass media. One of the most effective of these tools for children is television. The role of television gains importance in the development of children born and raised in an environment where television is present. The main purpose of the study is to investigate the role of television on children and to reveal whether the sexual content in television broadcasts has an effect on the sexual development of children. For this purpose, 385 subjects selected from 4 different regions in Konya participate in the study. The obtained findings provide integrity with the data obtained from face-to-face interviews. Broadcasts with sexual content in television series can be a factor in stimulating sexual urges in children before normal, and in children's getting sexual information and starting earlier than normal. Children who watch television less than 1 hour on weekdays and 1-3 hours on weekends want to be in the place of TV series actors. While sexual content attracts the attention of children, it does not allow watching horror and thriller broadcasts. It is among the results found in both quantitative and qualitative data that families who encounter obscene broadcasts next to children panic, change the television channel instead of giving information about the visual that the child sees, and stimulate the child's curiosity about the content they watch.

Keywords: Child, Adolescence, Media, Sex Education, Television

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TELEVİZYON YAYINLARINDA YER ALAN CİNSEL İÇERİKLERİN ÇOCUKLARIN GELİŞİMLERİ ÜZERİNDEKİ ROLÜNÜN İLİŞKİLER BAĞLAMINDA İNCELENMESİ

Seher Karataş*

Özet

İçinde bulunduğumuz yüzyılda, çocuk gelişimi ve kitle iletişim araçları arasında sıkı sıkıya bir ilişki vardır. Bu araçların, çocuklar için en etkili olanlarından biri ise televizyondur. Televizyonun olduğu ortamda doğan ve büyüyen çocukların gelişiminde televizyonun rolü önem kazanmaktadır. Çalışmanın temel amacı, televizyonun çocuklar üzerindeki rolünü araştırarak, televizyon yayınlarındaki cinsel içeriklerin çocukların cinsel gelişimlerinde etkisi olup olmadığını açığa çıkarmaktır. Bu amaçla gerçekleştirilen çalışmaya, Konya'nın 4 farklı bölgesinden seçilen 385 denek katılmaktadır. Edinilen bulgular, yüz yüze yapılan görüşmelerden elde edilen veriler ile bütünlük sağlamaktadır. Televizyon dizilerinde yer alan cinsel içerikli yayınlar, çocuklardaki cinsel dürtülerin normalden önce uyarılmasında ve çocukların cinsel bilgi edinmeye ve normalden önce başlamasında etken olabilmektedir. Televizyonu hafta içi 1 saatten az, hafta sonu 1-3 saat arası izleyen çocuklar dizi oyuncularının yerinde olmak istemektedir. Cinsel içerikler çocukların ilgisini çekerken, korku ve gerilim içerikli yayınları izlemeye izin vermemektedir. Müstehcen yayınlarla çocukların yanında karşılaşan ailelerin telaşa kapıldığı, gördüğü görsel hakkında bilgi vermek yerine televizyon kanalını değiştirdiği çocuğun izlediği içeriklerle ilgili merakının kamçulandığı hem nicel hem de nitel verilerde tespit edilen sonuçlar arasındadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Çocuk, Ergenlik, Medya, Cinsel Eğitim, Televizyon

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INTRODUCTION

Today, the importance of mass media is increasing day by day. Mass media has a feature that affects the society, guides and helps to form a habit. The possibility of accessing mass media at any time, making use of free time and especially entertaining features make people dependent on this tool. Children are one of the audience groups that are most vulnerable to messages given by mass media. Television plays the most active role among these tools.

Television has many effects on children. These effects are the effects on being a consumer society individual, the formation of sexual identity and relations with the opposite sex, the effect on the relationship with parents, the effect on violence tendencies, the effect on reading, thinking and success, the effect on the formation of their own identities, and the effect on the loss of childhood (Büyükbaykal, 2007, p. 35). The images in the broadcasts that the child is exposed to during the developmental period, under the influence of his parents, constitute a problem in the child's life to a large extent.

Children are the mirror held up to the future of a society. Therefore, the problems they experience in their development, their educational processes and the publications they watch are very important for their next period. The role of television broadcasts that children are exposed to in the development of the child is great.

Research is conducted on the role of sexual content in television broadcasts on the development of children, with the connection established between 'child, adolescence, media'. It is aimed to provide information about the effect level of sexual content broadcasts in television broadcasts on the development of children, based on previous studies and findings.

Child Development from Birth to the End of Adolescence

“A child's spiritual life is a wonderful thing; No matter what part of this life we deal with, it fascinates us. It is as if every act of the child reveals his life and personality in its entirety; therefore, it is impossible to comprehend a child's behavior without knowing this invisible background” (Adler, 2000, p. 22). As a society, raising healthy

generations is possible by raising individuals who are at peace with themselves and their environment physically, spiritually, mentally, socially and sexually.

From past to present, there are many factors that affect human behavior. Beginning from the prenatal period, past experiences, especially childhood, have a great impact on the behavior of people. When evaluating a person, it is necessary to evaluate his past and present together (Şişman, 2007, p. 157). The child, who grows up with the changes in the body in terms of weight and height, passes into the development phase and jumps to the maturation phase by containing many factors. Playing games, writing etc. for development. Learning that develops as a result of interaction with the environment is also an important dimension of development. From the first moment a person is born, he develops by learning and applying everything. Since it is known that the child will take every step with learning from the moment he is born, great importance should be given to the learning opportunities of the child in the developmental path.

Human development is a rich and detailed field from beginning to end. People have personal experience with development, but it is difficult to make sense of how and why people grow, learn everything, and why they behave the way they do. Child development stages provide a useful framework for thinking about human growth, development, and learning. It is clear that understanding the stages in determining what affects human thought and behavior will provide useful information to individuals and society (Cited by Hamamcı, 2015, p. 131). The characteristics and behaviors acquired by the child in the period when he does not know himself affect the next stages. Behaviors acquired for many reasons such as the attitude of the family towards the child, the environmental factor, and the basis of the problems that may be experienced in adolescence may arise from the behaviors acquired in the previous stages.

Children are attached to phases in a certain order from beginning to end. Depending on the child's current age, he may have gone through different stages of development and currently has other stages ahead of him to complete. Each stage occurs roughly at certain ages and requires the fulfillment of certain tasks for the child's development. When the child does not go through these learning stages in a normal

process, disorders in his development occur and other problems begin to erupt as he grows up (Mountrose, 2000, p. 139). Children who continue their normal development and follow the development line in a certain order complete their development and mature (Kaya, 1999, p. 81).

It is difficult to make precise age limits in terms of the beginning and ending of the main developmental periods such as childhood, adolescence/youth, adulthood and old age. However, due to the necessity brought by scientific studies, especially in studies conducted in the field of developmental psychology, age restrictions are made for each period related to developmental periods, although they are not the same in itself, but close to each other. (Koç, 2004, p. 232). The developmental stages basically consist of two parts as the prenatal period and the postnatal period. Since this study is a study on adolescent development, the first 2 years of infancy after birth, 3-6 years of first childhood (game), 7-11 years of primary school years, and 12-18 years of adolescence, which should be emphasized in the study, which is one of the stages of the postnatal period. period is considered.

Adolescence is a transitional period from childhood to adulthood in which a biological, psychological, mental and social development and maturation takes place. The development and maturity of the adolescent is generally an ongoing process. In the views on the stages in the development process, it is thought that each stage is based on the previous one and comes out of it (Yavuzer, 2005, p. 262). Normal behavior should not be expected during adolescence. Psychiatrists believe that all adolescents experience significant turmoil and confusion as they exit childhood (Orvin, 1999, p. 77).

Adolescent's identity develops gradually through different identifications made from childhood. Early adolescence children have some unclear images of their own identity. Adolescence is an important period in identity development and the adolescent seeks answers to questions about identity (Kulaksızoğlu, 1999, p. 106). His personality will be settled to the extent that he finds his adolescent identity and can get rid of the complexes. Identity; It is an individual's view of himself, which consists only of his own unique attitudes, feelings, perceptions, values, and behaviors. It is the subjective side of

personality (Yılmaz, 2014, p. 16). Adolescents lay the foundations for acquiring an identity during this period and their personality development gradually begins to take shape.

Expert Psychiatrist Recep Bostan, one of our qualitative participants, describes the development of emotions and thoughts of the adolescent, who encounters many physical and psychological stimuli until adolescence, in the transition from childhood to adolescence:

“ According to psychosocial and psychodynamic development, according to Freud's and Erikson 's theories, development progresses in stages, and in each process , the child has certain duties in encountering positive or negative stimuli. For example, a small child should have a good attachment process to the mother between the ages of 0-2. If this attachment process goes badly or if secure attachment does not occur, if positive stimuli are always present at these stages in adolescence, adulthood, and primary school age, a better transition to the next stage would be more appropriate. But when there is a negative stimulus, it will affect not only adolescence but also the whole personality structure, life, and the formation of other psychiatric disorders in the future. For every step, this is not just adolescence” (Bostan, interview dated 29.09.2016)

Emotional hurt is very important in sexual relations at an age when emotions are not yet mature, emotions go up and down, and emotions are not recognized. Experiencing sexual intercourse in the pre-adolescence period, when thoughts are not yet mature, is an event that can create many confusions later on. It may lead to an expression of the revolts of children who have entered the age of puberty in the new or early period, in search of independence and identity and identity, and the adolescent may want to prove this expression in the sexual sphere (Atabek, 2002, p. 165). should be held tight.

Sociologist Çalışkan, who draws attention to the psychological dimension of early adolescence, summarizes this situation as follows:

“ ... We are afraid of facing the inner world of the child, we are afraid to see what is missing, we say that the child has entered puberty and we get rid of it. Looking at society, it says adolescence between the ages of 10 and 21. Otherwise, there are those

who really enter physiologically. It is experienced in physiological changes where menstruation starts early, breasts grow early, and hair growth occurs. Doctors even try to delay it with some drugs, this is really early puberty, but not early puberty in behavior” (Çalışkan, interview dated 02.11.2016).

There is not always room for fear and worry in the face of the obvious signs of an early maturation of the child's sexual instinct. Some children's sexual development begins very early, in their first weeks of life. There is no need to panic when young children try to artificially stimulate their sense of sexual pleasure and sometimes the genitals of organisms. We should do our best to prevent the behavior in question, but we should not project the impression that we care too much about them. Children should not be allowed to access books that deal with sexual problems in a way that is incompatible with their age, and children should not be taken to movies that exploit the subject of sexuality (Adler, 2000, p. 181). Behaviors that will arouse sexual impulses and attract attention should be avoided, and the most important touchstone in the transition to adolescence is the sexual education process.

The sexual education of children and the period in which this education is given last until the adolescence years in accordance with the age (Aydınlı, 2002, p. 44). A child at the age of puberty should not be given a sexual education with skepticism, but a private education with a sense of trust (Güneş, 2014, p. 136). Since sexuality is a private subject, children do not come across examples of this in their environment, cannot make a comparison between what they see on television and real life, so they may believe that what they learn from television is true (Cited by İrkin, 2012, p. 75). The main problem of sexuality education is not only to enlighten children about the physiology of sexual relations, but also to prepare the child for love and marriage properly. Adolescents who do not have enough information on this subject will only make the subject of sexuality a subject of entertainment, and will only look at the related problem in terms of satisfying their sexual desires (Adler, 2000, p. 179).

Çalışkan, one of our qualitative research participants, who mentioned the importance of sexual education, expresses his views on this subject as follows:

“Sex education is one hundred percent important. First, you will give information to the child, you will tell what it is. This problem arises even in sexual therapies in the future; Vaginismus disease occurs in women who were suppressed in the family at the time, the woman cannot have intercourse, she is afraid... The problem of premature ejaculation in men is also caused by this deficiency. They don't know what sexuality is, they don't know what they're doing, they get pregnant in high school... I'm not saying that children should experience sexuality, but unfortunately they do, we cannot prevent it. At least something should go under control, not hurt them. It's not very healthy for a girl to have a child in high school. What are they doing, taking drugs and miscarrying the child. The child has an abortion at that age, and it is prevented from becoming a mother in the future” (Çalışkan, interview dated 02.11.2016).

Adolescents can get information about the changes in the growth and development period from their family, friends and some publications (Kulaksızoğlu, 1999, p. 56). Unless information and training on the subject is provided by persons and institutions equipped with sexuality, from time to time he may cause trouble with information pollution, false and unnecessary information he hears from the environment. Considering these risks, it is an appropriate approach to provide information about gender and sexuality in a more clear and instructive way both in educational institutions and within the family, in accordance with the developmental level of the child (Taner, 2011, p. 85; Aydınlı, 2002, p. 44). By giving the subject of sexual education only under the title of reproduction of people taught in classes, children get into a sense of curiosity and lead them to choose themselves, their parents, circle of friends and mass media as sources of questions about sexuality.

The Place and Effects of Television in Children's Lives

“Even children no longer believe in giants in fairy tales. In today's fairy tales, giants have been replaced by robots, space monsters, ambiguous good and evil creatures. The fairy tale giant of the past fell from both eyes and hearts. The tale fell out of favor, but such a giant entered human life that it was impossible for a single prince, knight or a commoner hero to cope with it. This giant, "electronic giant", that is, television, is a giant

that enters the most private areas of our family nest with a wave, takes up a lot of our time, and does not leave us alone even in our social relations ” (Mutlu, 2008, p. 13). Television is one of the most effective mass media today.

Until the middle of the 20th century, childhood is a protected period of human life against the outside world. The child dresses differently from the adult, behaves differently, the language he uses is different. There are words that the child does not want to hear. In recent years, there has been a definite transformation in the image and role of children thanks to television. Even if they are not completely similar, there are many similar behaviors between children and adults (cited by Timisi , 2011, p. 143-144). The most influential factor in this situation is undoubtedly television.

It is necessary to focus on the effects of television on children, which helps today's children to get out of the narrow family and close environment in which they live very early, and to realize that there are many different countries and people outside the country and people they live in (Can, 2006, p. 101). and teens buy more content than necessary for their age.

Although the reasons and ways of using the television between children and adults are different, everything is open to everyone on the screen. The child does not only watch children's programs, he has the habit of turning the television on and off early in the morning, like an adult. He enjoys the race to change channels. Using the television as a visual toy is among his daily interests. Meanwhile, he looks at anything that interests him. He learns all the secrets of the adult world through television, the modern means of disclosure. He can't help but feel like he's grown as he watches adult programs. In the early maturation process, he even underestimates and moves away from children's programs over time. With this aspect, television eliminates the level difference between the child and the adult (Şirin, 1998, p. 14). Children enjoy the visual richness by looking at the dizzying visuals with astonishment, but they actually become passive both physically and physically.

Many factors such as which broadcasts a child watches, how long he stays in front of the television, the behaviors acquired by children who grow up differently in cultural

and social aspects from television and the severity of being affected by it appear as variable factors in television-child interaction.

Young children are very curious to imitate what they see. When we look at the studies on the effects of TV, it is seen that the majority of them are aimed at revealing the negative (Turam, 1996, p. 40). Television keeps children away from play and friend environments, which are of great importance in terms of their personality development and socialization. Detachment from this environment negatively affects the success of the child in establishing social relations and making friends in his later life. The effects of television, which started at a young age, will continue throughout the child's life from the first developmental stage to the old age stage.

The real side effects of television can only be understood in the future, like pesticides, which are only understood after a generation has passed (Avcı, 1999, p. 98). The role of television on children is also seen at the cognitive level. It is seen that children often have a lack of attention, their brain functions become lazier and this indicates their academic success and reading comprehension problems. This situation is seen as an important obstacle that will negatively affect the future success and goals of children and young people affected by the media.

Time spent in front of the media replaces creative and active social pursuits. With long-term exposure, the media is more effective than parents and teachers in shaping the behavior and movements of young people, and it becomes a role example, the main source or the source of information (Çamurdan, 2007, p. 26). Although it has some positive benefits, it causes excessive television watching, inattention, stress, lack of concentration and eye disorder (Korkmaz, 1999, p. 126). Television broadcasts, which have a significant power over children, also affect children physically.

Children are also affected by television emotionally and psychologically. The child, who feels himself above the clouds with his imaginary world, may show fear, anxiety and aggressive behavior while hesitating between the images in the real world.

Undoubtedly, one of the important drawbacks of television is that it limits conversation, conversation and conversation within the family. Family members who

gather in the evenings spend hours facing the screen, trying to silence each other by minimizing conversation. Parents do not make their children talk when they watch their own TV shows, and the parents do not talk when children watch their own shows. The habit of TV has also reduced the traditional house tours and evening chats with friends in our country. Families get used to social loneliness and neighborly relations have weakened. The value judgments of families have begun to change and erode (Öztürk, 2002, p. 65). In this age where values and attitudes are questioned and it is realized that they are starting to disappear, the place of television should also be questioned. Children, who are vulnerable audiences, are the most affected by this situation.

At this point, it is seen that the mass media plays an important role in the effort to erase the differences between child and adult sexuality. In particular, TV not only puts the entire population in a state of high sexual excitement, but also emphasizes an egalitarian type of sexual intercourse. Sexuality transforms from a dark and deep adult secret to a product ready for everyone, something like mouthwash or armpit deodorant” (Postman, 1995, p. 174).

Murder, thriller and horror movies, characters that have nothing to do with reality like Superman, hit-and-miss shows like Ninja turtles, situations that encourage violence in movies called Spider-Man, programs that can mislead children and some individuals by always highlighting their body strength. stimulates sexual feelings. In short, the harmful aspects of television programs that advocate or encourage sex and violence and brute force are always the subject of criticism (Çakmaklı, 1997, p. 98-99).

On the other hand, Bostan, one of our qualitative research participants, emphasizes the effect of broadcasts with sexual content on children by saying, “... *broadcasts with sexual content and physical violence may cause the child to become curious about these issues at an early stage*” (Bostan, interview dated 29.09.2016).

Television broadcasts negatively affect children and youth. As the adolescent's attention is focused on sexual matters, his imagination will come into play and his mind will cease to dominate his situation. This is a very harmful situation for the spiritual development of young people. Instead of devoting his young mind to the age of

development, learning, working, increasing his culture and skills, in short, becoming a useful person for his nation by maturing, he will spend this energy on the path of his lust (Saygılı, 2002, p. 161). Çalışkan says the following about the role of sexual content in television broadcasts in the early stimulation of sexual impulses in children:

“...Children see early what they will experience in the future, what they will see in their body, and an anxiety begins; Why didn't I, why didn't my beard grow? This time, he is trying to use a razor early, masturbate early, and enlarge his penis. In other words, television teaches the child about sexuality in a completely wrong way” (Çalışkan, interview dated 02.11.2016) and underlines the need for parents to be careful in this regard. In order for television to cease to be a threat for children and adolescents and to turn it into a useful tool, adults who have a say in the shaping of the child's behavior from the birth of the child are aware of the harms of television and can try to minimize its negative effects by warning the child.

Method

Children who are exposed to violent content in the news and cartoons may perceive violence as an ordinary behavior and exhibit aggressive behavior. The dizzying visuals in the advertisements attract the attention of children and increase their consumption tendencies. Children who are not ready for sexual messages are exposed to sexual stimuli throughout the day through broadcast programs. Children who enter the adult world unprepared experience great problems when they are exposed to sexual content on television. Even though most adults can act consciously against these sexual contents, children can be negatively affected by these contents. This constitutes both the subject and the main problem of the research.

With this information, the universe of the research consists of students in the 1st and 4th grades of primary education in Meram, Karatay, Selçuklu districts of Konya. The sample of the study, on the other hand, consists of students from private and public primary schools, who were selected by random sampling method from the central districts of Konya province, taking into account the socio -economic situation, depending on the study population. |

In the research, questionnaire from quantitative research data collection techniques, literature review and interview technique from qualitative research data collection techniques are used as data collection techniques. The scales to be used in quantitative research are applied to students in the 1st and 4th grade range. In the analysis of the research data, the information obtained from the interviews with the experts is used in the research by putting it into writing.

The information obtained with the questionnaires was transferred to the electronic environment with SPSS 20.0 software and analyzed. In the first part, the distribution of the information obtained with the questionnaire was examined according to the schools and the relationship of the answers given with the school was examined by chi-square analysis. In the second part, the relationship of the answers given to some questions according to the schools was examined by chi-square analysis. Data were analyzed at 95% confidence level.

Findings and Interpretation

In the application part of our study called "The Role of Sexual Content in Television Broadcasts on the Development of Children", both quantitative and qualitative data are obtained. 385 samples participated in the application, which was carried out in 4 schools, 3 public and 1 private, selected from Meram, Selçuklu and Karatay Districts of Konya. Konya Meram 94 samples from Çayırbağı Tahsin- Özlem- Bengisu Emiroğlu Primary School, 108 samples from Meram Private Diltaş Primary School, 84 samples from Konya Karatay Feritpaşa Primary School and 99 samples from Konya Selçuklu İhsaniye Primary School were included in the research. 51.7% (198) of the samples were girls, 48.3% (185) were boys.

			School				Total	
			Çayırbağı	Diltaş	Feritpasa	İhsaniye		
How many hours do you watch TV on weekdays?	Less than 1 hour	N	44	53	49	39	185	
		%	48.4%	50.0%	59.8%	41.1%	49.5%	
	1-3 hours	N	32	39	24	38	133	
		%	35.2%	36.8%	29.3%	40.0%	35.6%	
	4-6 hours	N	6	6	8	16	36	
		%	6.6%	5.7%	9.8%	16.8%	9.6%	
	More than 6 hours	N	9	8	one	2	20	
		%	9.9%	7.5%	1.2%	2.1%	5.3%	
	Total		N	91	106	82	95	374
			%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Chi square=21,325; p=0.011

Table 1: Distribution of Daily Television Watching Hours by Schools on Weekdays

When the relationship between school and daily TV watching time on weekdays is examined; The rate of those who stated that they watched less than 1 hour out of a total of 374 people was 49.5%; The rate of those who stated that they watched 1-3 hours was 35.6%; The rate of those who stated that they watched it for 4-6 hours was 9.6%, while the rate of those who stated that they watched it for more than 6 hours was 5.4%. There is a significant relationship between school and daily TV watching hours on weekdays ($p < 0.05$).

			School				Total
			Çayırbağı	Diltaş	Feritpasa	İhsaniye	
How many hours of TV do	Less than 1 hour	N	33	30	44	18	125
		%	35.9%	28.0%	53.0%	18.4%	32.9%
	1-3 hours	N	36	46	30	46	158
		%					

you watch on the weekend?	4-6 hours	%	39.1%	43.0%	36.1%	46.9%	41.6%
		N	17	26	7	28	78
	More than 6 hours	%	18.5%	24.3%	8.4%	28.6%	20.5%
		N	6	5	2	6	19
Total	N	92	107	83	98	380	
	%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	

Chi square=30.707; p=0.000

Table 2: Distribution of Daily Television Watching Hours on Weekends by Schools

When the relationship between school and daily TV watching time on the weekend is examined; The rate of those who stated that they watched less than 1 hour out of a total of 380 people was 32.9%; The rate of those who stated that they watched 1-3 hours was 41.6%; The rate of those who state that they watch it for 4-6 hours is 20.5%, while the rate of those who state that they watch it for more than 6 hours is 5.0%. There is a significant relationship between school and daily TV watching time on the weekend ($p < 0.05$).

		School				Total	
		Çayırbağı	Diltaş	Feritpasa	İhsaniye		
Would you like to be in the place of one of the TV series actors?	Yes	N	56	51	52	54	213
		%	59.6%	47.2%	61.9%	54.5%	55.3%
	No	N	38	57	32	45	172
		%	40,4%	52,8%	38,1%	45,5%	44,7%
Total	N	94	108	84	99	385	
	%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	

Chi square =5, 051 ; p =0,168

Table 3: Distribution of the Status of Wanting to Be in the Place of the Actors of the TV Series by Schools

When the relationship between the school and the state of wanting to be in the place of one of the TV serial actors; 59.6% of Çayırbağı Primary School students; 47.2% of Diltaş Primary School students, 61.9% of Feritpaşa Primary School students; On the other hand, 54.5% of İhsaniye Primary School students stated that they would like to be in the place of one of the TV serial actors. There is no significant relationship between the school and the state of wanting to be in the place of one of the TV serial actors ($p>0.05$).

		School					Total
		Çayırbağı	Diltaş	Feritpaşa	İhsaniye		
What kind of programs does your family not allow you to watch?	Sexually explicit	N	20	12	14	10	56
		%	23.3%	12.4%	18.2%	11.6%	16.2%
	Violent	N	3	14	2	16	35
		%	3,5%	14.4%	2.6%	18.6%	10.1%
	Horror and thriller	N	23	40	26	24	113
		%	26.7%	41.2%	33.8%	27.9%	32.7%
	Publications that are pessimistic	N	2	4	5	6	17
		%	2.3%	4.1%	6.5%	7.0%	4.9%
	All can be tracked	N	8	3	5	12	28
		%	9.3%	3.1%	6.5%	14.0%	8.1%
	Soap opera	N	5	8	7	10	30
		%	5.8%	8.2%	9.1%	11.6%	8.7%
	Cartoon	N	22	3	9	3	37
		%	25.6%	3.1%	11.7%	3,5%	10.7%
	Other	N	3	13	9	5	30
		%	3,5%	13.4%	11.7%	5.8%	8.7%
Total		N	86	97	77	86	346
		%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Chi square = 69,791; $p=0.000$

Table 4: Distribution of Program Types Not Allowed by the Family by Schools

When the relationship between the school and the types of programs that the family does not allow to be watched; 16.2% of 346 people in total do not allow them to

watch broadcasts with sexual content, 10.1% with violence, 32.7% with horror and tension, and 4.9% with pessimism. The rate of those who do not allow watching TV series is 8.7%; While the rate of those who do not allow them to watch cartoons is 10.7%, the rate of those who do not allow them to watch other programs is 8.7% . The rate of those who gave the answer that they are all traceable is 8.1%. There is a significant relationship between the school and the types of programs that the family does not allow to be watched ($p < 0.05$).

			School				total	
			Çayırbağı	Diltaş	Feritpasa	İhsaniye		
What is the family's reaction in the hugging and kissing scenes in TV series?	They change the channel	N	83	67	66	79	295	
		%	88.3%	62.6%	81.5%	79.8%	77.4%	
	They're starting to get mad at the show	N	4	2	6	one	13	
		%	4.3%	1.9%	7.4%	1.0%	3.4%	
	They're asking me questions about the TV Show	N	2	0	one	2	5	
		%	2.1%	0.0%	1.2%	2.0%	1.3%	
	My family does not watch such programs with me.	N	3	27	6	15	51	
		%	3.2%	25.2%	7.4%	15.2%	13.4%	
	Other	N	2	11	2	2	17	
		,	2,1%	10,3%	2,5%	2,0%	4.5%	
	Total		N	94	107	81	99	381
			,	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

Chi square=45,600; $p=0,000$

Table 5: Distribution of Family's Reactions According to Schools in Hugging and Kissing Scenes in TV Series

When the relationship between the school and the family's reaction in the hugging and kissing scenes in TV series is examined; 77.4% of the total 381 people changed the channel; The rate of those who started to get angry with the serial is 3.4%. The rate of those who asked questions to the child about the broadcast series was 1.3%; The rate of those who stated that their families did not watch this type of TV series alongside the participants was 13.4%. The rate of those who reacted in the other way is 4.5%. There is

a significant relationship between the school and the family's reaction in the hugging and kissing scenes in TV series ($p < 0.05$).

Based on these findings, Expert Psychiatrist Recep Bostan, one of our qualitative research participants, underlined the following about the reaction of the family in the hug and kiss scenes on television:

“He should convey his interpretation of that image to the child without being too obvious. He should not remain unresponsive, he should convey his interpretation without being too reactive. For those who are not very cultured, the channel can be changed, but instead of changing the channel, appropriate comments should be conveyed to the child for people with a high socio -cultural level and who can explain this” (Bostan, interview dated 29.09.2016).

Stating that families have a responsibility in this regard, the Employee said;

“Instead of saying don't look, close, don't watch, get out of the room, he should be able to sit down and tell the child about his mistake. It is necessary to tell when it should happen and in what period it will happen. Children are no longer children we can trick like poison. That's why we need to give him real and accurate information, rather than cover it up. Otherwise, that child watches, tries to kiss at the age of 10, but when we tell him that he should do it with the person he marries, why it should be like this, from a religious, physiological, psychological point of view, we place something in the child's subconscious. Cover, cover, run, all of these make it more attractive and give the need to try it as soon as possible” (Çalışkan, interview dated 02.11.2016).

Specialist Psychologist Hakan Tokgöz, on the other hand, emphasizes that answers should be given according to the age of the child and expresses the following:

“...When children see the clear scenes on television broadcasts and see the uneasiness of their families, they start to ask “what's going on here” and fiddle more. The child asks his parents, and this should be given with answers appropriate to the child's age. Answers that are not age appropriate should be given. Our rule is that

whoever the child asks, he will answer. For example, father, I don't know, will not say ask your mother” (Tokgöz, interview dated 06.11.2016).

		School				Total		
		Çayırbağı	Diltaş	Feritpasa	İhsaniye			
What catches your attention the most in TV series?	Obscene content	N	42	28	18	24	112	
		%	47.2%	29.5%	25.0%	27.0%	32.5%	
	Horror-thriller content	N	3	7	8	21	39	
		%	3.4%	7.4%	11.1%	23.6%	11.3%	
	Violent content	N	27	10	18	24	79	
		%	30.3%	10.5%	25.0%	27.0%	22.9%	
	Publications that are pessimistic	N	0	0	2	3	5	
		%	0.0%	0.0%	2.8%	3.4%	1.4%	
	Nothing catches my attention	N	3	15	8	3	29	
		%	3.4%	15.8%	11.1%	3.4%	8.4%	
	Emotional	N	0	4	2	8	14	
		%	0.0%	4.2%	2.8%	9.0%	4.1%	
	Other	N	14	31	16	6	67	
		%	15.7%	32.6%	22.2%	6.7%	19.4%	
	Total		N	89	95	72	89	345
			%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Chi square= 79,736; p=0.000

Table 6: Distribution of Most Important Things in Television Series by Schools

When the relationship between school and the most striking thing in TV series is examined; The rate of those who answered sexual content out of 345 people in total is 32.5%. While the rate of those who gave the answer to the horror-thriller content was 11.3%, the rate of those who gave the answer to the broadcasts containing violence was 22.9%. The rate of those who stated that pessimistic publications attracted their attention was 1.4%; The rate of those who stated that emotional publications attracted their attention is 4.1%. While the rate of those who stated the other option was 19.4%, the rate of those who stated that nothing caught their attention was 8.4%. There was a significant relationship between school and the most striking thing in TV series ($p<0.05$).

Sociologist Nazlı Çalışkan, one of the qualitative research participants, draws attention to the role of publications with sexual content on children as follows:

“Today, we make a 10-year-old watch the TV series watched by the age of 30. Kissing in the scenes there affects the visual intelligence of the child. Children do not understand what is being told, we explain many things to them visually, we have them draw, we express, we go through the picture. The child records like a camera, also records the sexuality on television. This time he is curious about it, he wants to do it with the child. We don't care, we know what it is, but he doesn't. They even liken children to philosophy. Children are curious about everything. How will the child get an answer, he will get an answer by questioning. While the child is talking about the game on the computer, he says; “I put my dick between her ass, she said turn it off, I shut it then ahh ahh sounded out,” he says. This kid didn't experience sexuality here, it's all visual. It is not very right to attribute these to the parents, but the responsibility is in this respect, the parents should control what the child watches. Otherwise, all objects affect children” (Çalışkan, interview dated 02.11.2016).

Specialist Psychologist Hakan Tokgöz, on the other hand, underlines that publications with sexual content cause early arousal in children and mentions as follows:

“ I saw a boy saying, “Mom, when I see someone kissing on TV, my dick gets bigger”. The mother comes in terrified and tells us this. The child begins to enjoy the erogenous zone, the genital areas. When he is exposed to the stimulus he is not aware, the child does not know that it is sexuality. This should not be perceived as adult sexuality. If we normalize this too much within the family, children may be subject to unnecessary early stimulation. There is such a thing as taking pleasure in children” (Tokgöz, interview dated 06.11.2016).

Expert Psychiatrist Recep Bostan, one of our qualitative research participants, drew attention to the fact that publications with sexual content affect children:

“ It certainly increases sexual curiosity. Whatever the child watches, his curiosity about it increases. When this sexual content is broadcast, her curiosity about it increases. As a result, he goes on other searches related to it. From television to the

Internet, he learns other things. It can cause early awakening of sexual curiosity. Others, such as the domino effect, will in turn be earlier” (Bostan, interview dated 29.09.2016).

As can be deduced from the results of qualitative and quantitative research, publications with sexual content increase the curiosity of children. The frequency of kissing, hugging, kissing, making love, friendship, love answers to the open-ended questions included in the category of sexually explicit publications in the scales applied to children aged 7-10 who say that they are influenced by the movie they watch and attract their attention to the broadcasts with sexual content draws attention.

CONCLUSION

As the period when sexual curiosity begins, the family attitude in the first childhood period, that is, in the 0-6 age period, gains importance. The child becomes aware of the organs of the opposite sex and in his own body and tries to satisfy his curiosity in an effort to ask questions. Expert Psychologist Hakan Tokgöz says, “...*the period when the foundations of personality are laid is between the ages of 0-6. After that, whether people reach the age of 40 or reach the age of 60, they will return and experience problems between the ages of 0-1 or between the ages of 3-6, and drew attention to the fact that the foundations of this period should be laid solid.*

The role of mass media is gaining importance as another factor that increases his curiosity about sexual issues. The child, who raises awareness with the reaction of the parents in the sexually content broadcasts he sees on television, tries to ask questions. What is the reaction of the family in the hugging and kissing scenes of the students participating in our study in TV series? To the question, 77.4% replied that they are changing the channel. Sociologist Nazlı Çalışkan “.. *cover, close, run, all of these make it more attractive and give the need to try it as soon as possible.*” He says that the attitude of the family, who does not know how to behave in such a situation, attracts the attention of the children and causes them to research these issues.

Parents, who consider it a shame and sin to talk about sexual matters, do not talk about sexual matters at all. This approach causes the child to think that he should suppress his curiosity about this subject, and thus sexuality becomes taboo and even thinking is

forbidden. Thus, the child becomes silent, stops asking questions, but cannot help satisfying his curiosity. In this case, the greatest danger is that the child turns to mass media, where he will receive much more information than necessary.

Television, one of the mass media, stimulates the child's curiosity about sexual matters, given the easy accessibility of the child. Children who watch the same programs as their family members get a sense of wonder when they see the images in the obscene broadcasts on the television broadcasts. Participants, what catches your attention the most on TV? With the answers to the open -ended question, kissing, hugging, shameful things, perverted things, friendship, 32.5 % said that sexual content attracted their attention, 22.9 % said that broadcasts with violent content, 11.3% said that broadcasts with horror-thriller content attracted their attention. What show does your family not allow you to watch? While 32.7 % of the participants gave answers to the open-ended question, such as blood, fight and fight, broadcasts containing horror and tension were given, while broadcasts with sexual content were 16.2%.

The family has great responsibilities in this regard. First of all, parents should choose the right channels that they can watch together on TV and should not leave their children alone in front of the TV. When broadcasts that are not suitable for children come across on television, they should not be changed in a hurry, and the child should be reminded that he should face the problem by asking questions. The sexual education to be given to children should be given in accordance with their age from the moment the child starts to ask questions. It will be the parents' responsibility to keep the adolescent, who has completed the child's developmental stages and reached adolescence, away from early sexual stimuli. With the effect of developing and increasing hormones during this period, your child, who wants to relieve sexual tension, may want to have a sexual experience. *“It is also wrong to respect the child's ideas, to support his thoughts, to be understood by speaking instead of suppressing, to reduce the pressure and authority, to keep the boundaries completely free, and to be like a friend with the child. “Expert Psychiatrist Recep Bostan draws attention to the importance of the family in this period. In this period, in the words of Specialist Psychologist Hakan Tokgöz, “adolescents should not be released completely, nor should they be put under pressure”.*

Parents are very important and valuable for children. The control mechanism of the mother and father makes the adolescent feel that sexual safety is the responsibility of the parents. Sociologist Nazlı Çalışkan says “...*the families and the environment do this, the child is in adolescence and steps aside. That makes the family's job easier.*” He mentions that the family ignores the child during this period. Without seeing sexuality as a taboo, the child should be prepared for puberty whenever he wants, without giving evasive answers.

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